

NEWSLETTER

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In the rapidly evolving landscape of social innovation and public service transformation, the DECIDO project emerges as a pioneer in utilizing cutting-edge methodologies like Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA), Behaviour Change Games (BCG), and Processes Digital Twins. ”

Co-creation and Challenges of Citizen Engagement in the DECIDO Project: Navigating Social Life Cycle Assessment, Behaviour Change Games, and Ethical Concerns

This ambitious initiative aims to instigate a shift towards deliberative attitudes within communities, utilizing Serious Games as a tool for behavioural change. However, this innovative approach is not without its challenges, particularly in the realms of data privacy, ethical considerations, and the evolving landscape of social performance assessment.

S-LCA serves as a potent methodology for assessing the social and socio-economic impacts of public services, stretching from emergency management to the handling of food waste

and refugees. Yet, the absence of standardized methodologies poses a challenge, albeit one that the DECIDO project confronts with the adoption of guidelines published by UNEP/SETAC Life Cycle Initiative. The integration of Processes Twins within the Serious Gaming framework allows for a dynamic representation of real-world processes, enabling a comprehensive assessment of social impacts.

On the other hand, the advent of Behaviour Change Games (BCG) introduces a unique dimension to the DECIDO project. Leveraging the

popularity of games for leisure, BCGs aim to influence real-world behaviours by aligning game processes with users' daily contexts. The incorporation of Self-Determination Theory (SDT) and Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) underscores the importance of motivational orientation and belief systems in shaping behavioural change. However, the ethical implications of profiling communities for targeted behaviour modification necessitate stringent adherence to GDPR regulations, urging the project to obtain informed consent and conduct Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIA).

The intersection of S-LCA and BCG within the DECIDO project introduces a complex interplay, accentuating the need for a propaedeutic framework. This framework, encompassing three phases—Process Twin preparation, S-LCA application, and BCG simulation—requires a delicate balance between innovation and ethical considerations. The potential risks, including hidden privacy issues during Process Twin preparation and the clash between BCG and TPB approaches, underscore the necessity of external ethical audits and continuous GDPR compliance.

The DECIDO project's journey unveils a transparent and positive experimentation with these methodologies, highlighting the importance of Engagement, Involvement, and Accountability. The integration of DECIDO with EOSC services emerges as a comprehensive solution, covering the entire spectrum of Social Lifecycle Assessment processes. For stakeholders' engagement and involvement, DECIDO leverages its platform and services, ensuring a seamless evaluation of simulated policies. The reliance on EOSC services for data collection and analytics attests to the project's commitment to accountability and data-driven decision-making.

As the DECIDO project navigates the challenges of co-creating a transformative approach to citizen engagement, it stands at the forefront of pioneering methodologies that have the potential to shape the future of social innovation and public services. However, the ethical considerations and privacy challenges demand continual scrutiny and adaptation, ensuring that the project's positive impact is not overshadowed by unintended consequences.

The DECIDO Portal: Supporting Policy Processes with Evidence

In the dynamic landscape of policy-making, the integration of data-driven approaches has become increasingly important. There are certain barriers to such approaches as they require expertise and multiple data tools. This is the context which inspired the DECIDO platform, a comprehensive set of tools designed to empower policy-makers with the means to initiate, manage, and conclude data-informed policies effectively. At the heart of this innovative solution lies the DECIDO portal, a centralized hub facilitating seamless integration of data into the policy-making process.

The DECIDO platform offers policy makers a compact set of tools to initiate, manage and conclude data-driven policies. The tools allow the users to gather, store and visualize data relevant to policy making processes. Additionally, the user can link the data to the different steps of the policy making process using the DECIDO portal.

The architecture of the DECIDO platforms is based on micro-services. The services selected or implemented as part of the project offer data capabilities complementary to the various phases of the policy making, such as agenda setting, policy formulation, policy implementation, and policy evaluation. Users have the flexibility to use the toolbox based on their current policy-making needs, whether it's gathering, analysing, or visualizing data. Additionally, the tools facilitate discussions with stakeholders and citizens.

The following services are part of the current DECIDO platform:

- DECIDO Portal (Backend and frontend)
- DECIDO Dashboard (Grafana)
- DECIDO Co-creation (Discourse)
- DECIDO Data-Editor (Grist)
- DECIDO Data Catalogue (Piveau)
- DECIDO Survey (Limesurvey)
- DECIDO DataHub (EGI DataHub)
- DECIDO Data Notebook (EGI Jupiter Hub)

This collection offers a comprehensive toolbox for data-driven policy making. At the heart of this toolbox is the DECIDO portal, which plays a crucial role in connecting various data operations to the policy making process. Furthermore, the DECIDO portal offers a structured methodology that allows keeping a log of the entire policy making process, while bolstering each phase with data evidence generated using other tools.

The architecture of the DECIDO platform has been revamped for the final version of the portal. The architecture follows the concept of data-driven policies, and it connects the policy

making process with the toolbox of DECIDO. For this purpose, an integration layer based was introduced.

In summary, the DECIDO platform represents a paradigm shift in policy-making, where evidence-based decision-making is not just a possibility but a reality. By seamlessly integrating data into the policy-making process, DECIDO empowers users to make informed decisions, fostering more effective and inclusive governance.

Paving the way for impactful evidence-based policymaking

The landscape of public administration faces constant and important challenges when it comes to making its operations more efficient, more effective, and more transparent. The DECIDO project has emerged as a beacon of innovation, reshaping the way policy decisions are informed and implemented across Europe. Spearheaded by a consortium of leading organisations, DECIDO has introduced groundbreaking methodologies, tools, and knowledge, facilitating the development of evidence-based policies by public administrations.

At the heart of DECIDO's mission lies the commitment to bridge the gap among public administrations, citizen science, and state-of-the-art technologies like cloud technologies and big data. By leveraging the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), and effective new technological tools developed by the consortium's technical partners, DECIDO enables public administrations to exactly harness the potential of the aforementioned technologies. This initiative is set against the backdrop of four pivotal pilots across Europe.

DECIDO's comprehensive approach encompasses the entire policymaking lifecycle, emphasising the active involvement of local actors in data generation and analysis. Through the project's activities, the ambitious objectives of facilitating the adoption of data analytics and cloud infrastructure in policymaking and ensuring that data contributes effectively to evidence-based decision-making processes aligned with political objectives and priorities can now be considered a realistic scenario.

One of the project's standout achievements is the development of a comprehensive roadmap, structured around the DECIDO Transition Scenarios and complemented by a robust set of policy recommendations. These scenarios envision a future where DECIDO's impact is fully realised, outlining the changes needed to reach this future state. The recommendations, accompanied by targeted metadata, address legal, procedural, societal, and technological themes, offering intelligence to public administrations on how to navigate the transition towards more informed,

evidence-based and effective policies.

The DECIDO project not only exemplifies the power of collaborative innovation in the public sector but also sets a precedent for future initiatives aimed at enhancing the efficiency, effectiveness, and responsiveness of policymaking mechanisms. By fostering a co-creative environment and leveraging cutting-edge technologies, DECIDO paves the way for a more engaged, informed, and empowered approach to public administration, promising a brighter, more resilient future for European citizens and beyond.

VOL.TO AND THE DECIDO EXPLOITATION STRATEGY: WHAT'S NEXT?

Once the H2020 DECIDO project is over, the partner Volontariato Torino (Vol.To ETS) is committed to exploit the co-creation methodology developed and tested during the project. In particular, it will promote the dissemination and use of the social hackathon strategy - appropriately moderated by an expert facilitator - as a co-decision-making tool in order to find shared solutions among several actors (citizens, civil society organisations, companies and public bodies) to issues that may affect several scenarios (not only emergency ones).

The use of this methodology, even after the project has ended, will serve to maximise, in particular, the two Key Exploitable Results (KERs) inherent to the “DECIDO Approach for Evidence-Based Policy Making” and the “Co-creation Methodology”.

The dissemination of the co-creation methodology tested within DECIDO will initially concern the pool of 1300 associations in the Metropolitan City of Turin (Italy) to which, by institutional mandate, Vol.To ETS provides free logistical and consulting services. However, it will potentially soon be extended to the whole of Italy and the European Union. While for local associations - in the territory in which Vol.To has jurisdiction - the service of sharing the co-creation methodology will be free of charge, for other private entities in the Metropolitan City of Turin and for any organisation outside this territory the service will be chargeable, thus configuring the possibility of commercially exploiting the methodology itself. To make this long-term sustainability strategy

more effective, a space has been set up within the Vol.To ETS headquarters to host an ad hoc division that will be responsible for disseminating and promoting the co-creation and social hackathon tool on a large scale, in order to increase knowledge and interest on the part of potential users.

The staff of the organisations joining the initiative will be appropriately trained on the DECIDO methodology and accompanied in the first occasions of its application, so that they can make the most of its full potential. The DECIDO Portal will be indicated as one of the possible IT platforms to be used to support each co-creation session, e.g. to keep track of what has been discussed or decided, as a repository of data and documents, as a tool to analyse the collected data. The use of other platforms on the market, e.g. Confluence, WordPress or Trello, is not excluded.

The co-creation methodology developed and tested through the DECIDO project will be used in all future Vol.To projects in which co-design together with a group of citizens, associations and other stakeholders is planned.

Furthermore, it will be crucial to find external funding to ensure budget coverage of all cost items envisaged for the promotion and dissemination of the DECIDO methodology (staff, dedicated space, event costs, etc.) and for the data and platform maintenance and evolution. These funds may come from bank foundations and/or local, national and European calls for funding.

BRIDGING INNOVATIONS & EXPLOITATION: WHAT COMES NEXT?: 2024

The DECIDO project recognizes that the sustainability of technologies relies on the convergence of social and economic impacts it generates. Exploitation opportunities have been pinpointed, considering specific target groups and insights from pilots and Key Exploitable Result (KER) owners.

The envisioned joint DECIDO exploitation plan articulates two primary objectives:

- Establish a collaborative framework among DECIDO partners to exploit project results through ongoing collaboration, knowledge exchange, research activities, innovation, and developments, particularly with Public Authorities (PAs). This involves laying the groundwork for the EOSC Competence Center for Public Authorities, aiming to leverage research outcomes, facilitate technological transfer, secure collaborations and scout funding opportunities from both public and private entities to sustain project development.
- Valorize the core outcomes of the DECIDO project for wider impact and enable individual exploitation by consortium partners, empowering them to leverage the KERs.

The final Exploitation Plan delineates the vision for utilizing project outcomes post-funding period, specifying objectives, requirements, and the approach to ensure DECIDO's sustainability in the medium to long term. Initiatives include the intent of formalizing a DECIDO consortium, setting the ground for the "DECIDO-Alliance for the Exploitation of DECIDO Key Exploitable Results" and the "EOSC Competence Center for Public Authorities Communities and Membership Charters", focusing on valorising DECIDO results and collaborating with public and private entities for ongoing and future project development.

DECIDO's innovative approach to policy-making has the potential to transform how policies are created and improved across a variety of markets. Its data-driven, stakeholder-inclusive methodo-

logy ensures that policies are not only effective but also responsive to the needs and insights of those they impact.

The DECIDO consortium partners plan to offer and bundle different functionalities of the DECIDO Portal; the platform with all the services and features is also planned to be offered as a consultancy service.

Unique in its design and vision, the DECIDO solution offers immense potential to be leveraged as both a Platform as a Service (PaaS) and a Consultancy Service.

By utilizing DECIDO as a PaaS, users are provided with a complete cloud-based development and deployment environment, enabling the efficient delivery of applications ranging from simple cloud-based ones to more complex, multi-tiered cloud-enabled enterprise applications.

As a PaaS, DECIDO helps users, particularly policy-makers and public authorities, to minimize the costs and complexities associated with buying, managing, and supporting the underlying infrastructure and software. This allows users to focus on the deployment and management of their applications, leading to greater operational efficiency and cost-effectiveness.

In addition to being a PaaS, DECIDO can also be leveraged as a Consultancy Service. As a consultancy, DECIDO can offer expert guidance to policy actors to enable them to effectively navigate and adopt the provided services.

This consultancy approach can play an invaluable role in training policy actors in the understanding and application of the co-creation methodology, use of the web portal, interpretation of data insights, and in the overall adoption of a data-driven, participatory approach to policy making.

DECIDO presents excellent value as both a platform as a service and a consultancy service. The innovative blend of these two aspects provides a versatile and comprehensive solution for policy-making. Whether it is through a cloud-based developmental environment, a user-friendly portal for policy-making, or through expert guidance and custom solutions, DECIDO stands as a valuable tool that can revolutionize how policies are made, implemented, and evaluated.

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